

A global and dynamic completeness assessment of the OpenStreetMap buildings

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The OpenStreetMap (OSM) building dataset is rapidly expanding at a rate of approximately five million buildings per month, or approx. 2 buildings per second. Contributions range from hobbyists mapping an area, official registries that are imported, to the mapping by humanitarian organizations. The joint efforts lead to a non-uniform result, with some regions well-mapped, while others are lacking basic geographic features. The status quo of building completeness is desirable to identify areas on a global scale where OSM is (almost) complete but also where the most effort is needed. Furthermore, because of the non-uniformity, it can be useful to know for the end user if any buildings are missing at their location of interest.

A map is never complete and the ever-changing dataset of OSM embodies this well. With digital maps, where the map scale becomes a fuzzy concept, more details can be added any time and one can improve the accuracy of geometries endlessly. For us, an area is considered complete, as long as all the buildings have been mapped and the footprints follow the outline of the building roughly. Attributes, such as the height, have been disregarded in this research, but are well researched in [1]. Other factors, such as the time of the last modification of a building have been looked at by [2,3]. Also the quality of the building geometry has been well researched [4–6], but was not considered in this research.

We create a dynamic assessment of the completeness of OSM buildings on a global scale. While completeness assessment datasets exist on a small scale [7,8], near-global scale [9,2], or even global scale [10], human development and the nature of OSM ensures that as soon as such a dataset is published, it is already outdated. For a meaningful completeness assessment, it is crucial to update it the moment that a building is added, modified or removed.

Semi-automatically generated datasets based on earth observation data and Machine Learning have been assessed to be used as reference models. These include the Global Human Settlement Layer (GHSL) of 2022 [11], Microsoft Building Footprints [12], and Google Open Buildings [13]. Contrary to the other datasets, GHSL is raster-based, with pixels indicating whether an area contains built up areas. The raster files were vectorized, so that

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they can be used in the same manner as the other datasets. We have carefully examined these datasets and decided that the Google buildings have the most accurate footprints, followed by the GHSL dataset. The GHSL dataset, due to its nature as a 10x10 meter resolution raster dataset, consistently overestimates the built-up area compared to OSM. The Microsoft dataset, while covering most countries in the world, is itself incomplete in many areas. The data is very inconsistent: even within cities there can be well-covered areas as well as areas missing altogether. As the coverage of buildings in OSM in many areas is of much better quality, we deemed the Microsoft dataset unfit for the purpose of completeness estimation. The Google dataset seems to have the most complete estimate for the countries that they provide. Therefore we used the Google buildings for countries when available and otherwise used GHSL.

An initial state of OSM completeness was computed on an OSM planet file generated reflecting the exact building data of 1 January 2022, midnight UTC. The built area of OSM and the proxy datasets have been computed on a Quadtree grid using level-18 tiles. Their size is approximately 100x100 meters in Europe and slightly larger than 150x150 meters near the equator. As there are 64 billion of such tiles, a recursive method is used for calculation. It is initiated on a level-1 grid, which divides the world into four tiles. For each tile, it is checked whether it contains any built area and if it does, it is divided into four new tiles. This process is repeated for all resulting tiles of the next zoom level, until the level-18 has been reached. For this zoom level, the total square meter of built area within each tile is calculated for the OSM and proxy datasets. Finally, they are compared to each other to estimate the completeness. The data have been aggregated to level-15 tiles (between 800x800 and 1200x1200 meter), to examine the differences between aggregation levels. The result of the level-15 tiles can be found in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Building completeness of OSM on 1 January 2023, aggregated onto zoom-level-13 Quadkey tiles.

We have identified a list of countries (e.g. France; the Netherlands; Denmark) that we consider to be complete, partly through knowledge of imports and partly through our own

judgment. For these countries we assessed the accuracy of the completeness assessment using the GHSL dataset and we found that the level-15 tiles were more reliable to use, due to the quality of the data in the proxy dataset. As the GHSL dataset has a resolution of 10x10 meter pixels, it is not as detailed as the OSM buildings. Therefore, not only is there a consistent overestimation of built area in the proxy dataset, there may also be false positive built area in some tiles. A level-15 resolution provides a less precise assessment, but a better result. Therefore there is a trade-off between accuracy and precision, where at a larger scale the level-15 assessment is preferred, while at a smaller scale (e.g. a city), the grid of ~1x1 kilometer is a bit coarse. Unfortunately, none of the countries within the coverage of the Google dataset are considered complete in OSM, therefore such validation of the results cannot be made.

Building changes are detected on a minute-by-minute basis. A change in a building geometry triggers a recalculation of the built area of the tile(s) intersecting the building. Also the comparison between the proxy dataset and the building dataset is recalculated. In this way, each change to buildings in OSM is detected and processed to produce a completeness map that is always up-to-date with the latest changes.

The project was built using the Overpass API [14], with the augmented diffs tracking the minutely changes. The Osmium tool [15] has been used to replicate the complete OSM building dataset, for fast processing. All code that is used in this project is available on our GitLab under the GNU AGPLv3 license (<https://git.gfz-potsdam.de/globaldynamicexposure>). The data that are continuously produced for this project are made available under ODbL and can be found at <https://www.openbuildingmap.org/>. GHSL, Google Open Buildings and OSM are all open datasets, with the latter two also found under the ODbL license.

The OSM community has always been divided on whether large datasets should be imported into OSM [16]. Importing them directly has many disadvantages. For example, the footprints of the buildings can be crooked and not represent the actual shapes of the building. However, both datasets by Google and Microsoft contain many buildings not present in OSM at all. This research brings us one step closer to a practical purpose, where the tiles that are considered incomplete, compared to the reference datasets can be highlighted per region or country. One of the main applications can be found in the addition of buildings to OSM, even more so in cases when it needs to be decided quickly where the most buildings need to be added geographically, such as humanitarian mapping efforts in the event of a disaster. Our work can be used complementary to the efforts in MapSwipe, where one can manually assess the completeness of the OSM building dataset, because MapSwipe uses the same tiling system [17]. An up-to-date completeness assessment can also greatly benefit users of OSM data for various applications. While a complete dataset does not automatically result in data of good quality, we know for certain that there is a lack of quality when the dataset is not complete. On top of that we can identify not only the most incomplete areas, but also the most incomplete areas that do not have a lot of mapping activity over time.

Further effort is needed to validate the completeness estimation, for example by using up-to-date registry datasets of areas that are not yet complete in OSM. The completeness estimation could be improved, by using other data sources, such as the proximity to OSM street networks, that could indicate the likelihood of a building existing in a proxy dataset.

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